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¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

- R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

- PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

List of Abbreviations and definitions

The abbreviations and definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary³.

³ <https://www.aidava.eu/helpdesk/glossary>

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1 Introduction	5
2 Description of Activities	5
3 Problem to be solved	7
3.1 A concrete example of health data quality issues for reuse	7
3.2 Overview of the problem we want to solve	9
3.3 First Core problem to be solved: Data aggregation & curation	10
3.4 Second Core problem to be solved: Patient involvement	11
4. Description of Use Cases	14
4.1 Use Case 1. Toward a EU cross-border Breast Cancer registry	14
Introduction to existing breast cancer registries	14
Current approach and issues	16
Proposed approach with AIDAVA	17
Proposed Data sources	20
4.2 Use Case 2. Secondary prevention of Atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease	21
Introduction to longitudinal health record for CVD patients	21
Currents approach and issues	22
Proposed approach	23
Proposed Data Sources	26
5 Evaluation criteria to measure performance of prototype	27
5.1. Metrics defined in the proposal	27
5.2. Update of metrics after brainstorming session	29
6 Resources needed for deployment & testing	30
6.1. Description of the site questionnaire	30
6.2. Overview of the answers across sites	31
7 Conclusion	31
8 Next steps	32
9 References	32
10 Annexes	33
10.1 Patient empowerment - EHN (Cardio)	33
10.2 Patient empowerment - ECPC (Breast cancer)	34
10.3 System usability Scale (Standard version)	35

Executive Summary

This deliverable clarifies the problem to be solved in AIDAVA, i.e. (1) develop a "data cleaning" machine with maximum automation in curation and publishing of personal healthcare data and (2) maximise engagement with the patients in the curation process of these data when automation is not possible. The deliverable then describes the 2 use cases for testing the prototype: (1) the first use case is hospital centric and will demonstrate feasibility of a federated "EU" breast cancer registry composed by **interoperable** extracts issued from multiples different sources from each of the evaluation sites; (2) the second use case is patient-centric and will demonstrate how patient data curated into an individual longitudinal health record can be **reused** for visualising of the patient record and for computing a cardiac risk score supporting physicians in monitoring risk for their patients. We will also explore the possibility of presenting the risk score to the patient.

Finally, the deliverable provides more information on the metrics that will support assessment of the prototype and identify key elements to be taken into account when deploying the prototype across sites.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is the result of Task 1.1. in Work Package 1 with 3 streams of work.

- Scoping the problem to be solved, based on a description of issues around curation and extraction of information for patient registries and personal longitudinal record EHRs.
- Consolidating the expected outcome from the project, including evaluation criteria supporting assessment.
- Identifying resources needed in each evaluation site to support deployment and testing of the prototype, taking into account resources, data privacy aspects and technical constraints on each site.

Following the description of the activities in Chapter 2, this deliverable includes further 4 chapters:

- Chapter 3. Description of the problem to be solved, including core aspects and enablers, and ensure alignment across the project stakeholders
- Chapter 4. Description of the 2 uses cases, following discussion with our clinical experts, to support the development, deployment and testing of the 2 generations of the AIDAVA virtual assistant prototype
- Chapter 5. Specification of the evaluation criteria that will be used to check the performance of the prototype
- Chapter 6. Identification of the key resources to be managed during the project to ensure smooth deployment and testing in each site.

2 Description of Activities

In this specific task, we followed a co-creation approach across the different participants: we organised bi-weekly meetings of 2 hours between mid-September and mid-February, and had 2 face to face workshops (4 and 5 October 2022 in Maastricht as part of the Kick-off meeting, 6 to 8 December 2022 in Tallinn as a joint workshop across Tasks 1.1, 2.1 and 4.1).

We first worked on ensuring alignment on the scope of the project. NEMC and b!lo created a first questionnaire with the following questions:

1. what is the problem we want to solve in the AIDAVA project,
2. who are the expected users of the AIDAVA virtual assistant prototype,
3. what do we mean by patient empowerment,
4. what are your expectations of the project - and the prototype,
5. what are the available data sources in your organisation in scope of the prototype.

Each partner provided their answers; the results were discussed during the bi-weekly meetings.

Consolidation of the answers to questions 1, 2 and 3 took place during the brainstorming sessions at the October workshop in Maastricht and led to the content of Chapter 3. In addition, we checked our assumption on patient empowerment with "patient consultants"⁴ during a brainstorming session in January 2023.

We confirmed the consortium understanding of the project - and related expectations described in answers to question 4 - by further detailing the 2 use cases through our regular meetings. Discussion on the use cases specifically considered the expected benefits for patients, clinicians and the organisation. Description of the use cases is provided in Chapter 4.

Development of the expected outcomes of the project built on the 4 metrics identified in the proposal took place mainly during brainstorming sessions at the December 2022 workshop in Tallinn. The result is detailed in Chapter 5; the proposed metrics will be further developed in the assessment protocol as part of Task 1.4.

For Chapter 6, we developed a questionnaire to check different aspects needed to ensure a smooth deployment of the AIDAVA prototype in the target sites; this included the following questions.

- Overview of the current situation of each use case in each organisation and related expectations; this helped us to understand existing issues and manage expectations with local teams on what problems AIDAVA will solve (and what it will not address as it is out of scope).
- Identification of requirements from local committees and boards (e.g., Ethical Committee) and specific departments (e.g., access to IT staff and server) that must be handled to support smooth deployment and testing.
- Detailed description of available data sources to be used by the prototype (with consent of the patient).
- Implementation of Data Portability within the site to support extracting of information for the site by the patient.
- Availability/experience around Data Transfer Agreements, between Health Data Intermediary (HDI), managing patient's personal data, and data source providers such as personal app or medical devices, and between HDI and hospitals.
- High level technical requirements to allow deployment of the AIDAVA prototype within a testing site and identification of potential showstoppers.

⁴ Patient consultants are patients selected by the 2 patient organisations - based on predefined "inclusion/exclusion criteria" - who agreed to work throughout the project as consultant/ advisors representing the views from patients. Each organisation selected 4 patient consultants; these patients are not expected to share any personal data.

- High level descriptions of potential data flows between the different entities and components (In alignment with Task 4.1).

The 5 deployment sites - 3 hospitals (NEMC, UM, MUG) and 2 Health Data Intermediaries (DME, MID) - answered the questionnaire. The answers were discussed at the December workshop in Tallinn to ensure common view across the partners.

3 Problem to be solved

3.1 A concrete example of health data quality issues for reuse

Availability of integrated, high-quality personal health data (PHD) remains limited, with impact on quality & cost of care and limiting possibilities for research and analytics. Indeed, PHD is currently distributed, heterogeneous, captured through different modalities, with variable quality. Findability and accessibility of this data is the first step and is addressed in numerous projects ([Kalendralis et al. 2021](#)), ([Queralt-Rosinach et al. 2022](#)), interoperability and reuse of this data remains a major challenge due to several factors - this is addressed in the AIDAVA project.

	Summary in GP's file (paper)	Lab result (electronic file)	EHR (electronic file)	Imaging (electronic file)									
Same doctor?	From: Dr John Smith Patient: Adele X	Requestor: J. Smith Patient: Adele X	Treating Dr: J Ed Smith Patient: Adele X	Physician: J Smith Patient: A. X									
Same time/visit?	Visit: 07/09/21	Request date: 09/07/2021	September, 1 st , 2021	Date: 09/07/2021									
Different units	The patient was diagnosed with diabetes 2 in 2011. She complained about regular tiredness and nausea... And is overweighted .	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Chemistry</th> <th>value</th> <th>range</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Blood Glucose</td> <td>6 mmol/l</td> <td>4-7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Urine Glucose</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Chemistry	value	range	Blood Glucose	6 mmol/l	4-7	Urine Glucose			Blood glucose= 120 mg/dl	
Chemistry	value	range											
Blood Glucose	6 mmol/l	4-7											
Urine Glucose													
No unit?	Physical exams showed BP of 6/10 Lab test done today: ... Scan displayed... Diagnosis: Depression due to .. Treatment: keep metformin same dosage; follow if symptoms persist	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Hematology</th> <th></th> <th></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Hemoglobine</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hematocrit</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Hematology			Hemoglobine			Hematocrit			SBP = 130 mmHG DBP = 90 mmHG	
Hematology													
Hemoglobine													
Hematocrit													

Figure 1. Example of health data and data quality issues

Figure 1 displays 4 different data sources related to the same patient:

- GP's notes – in paper format, scanned through OCR to produce an electronic text file
- Lab result – in electronic file (potentially structured in LOINC format)
- EHR – electronic file (potentially structured in HL7 format)
- Medical image (potentially in DICOM electronic format with metadata)

This example shows different data quality issues for reuse:

- The paper document with GP notes is transformed in an electronic format containing a clinical narrative that must be processed to extract the key clinical information. This is typically solved by using Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools.
- The GP record specifies “BP of 6/10” which is terse ... no full wording, no unit. This happens regularly in paper records to “win time” for the treating side. It is possible – with trained AI/NLP algorithms – to recognize that this means Blood Pressure of 6 cmHG for diastolic and 10 cmHG for systolic, and then transform this into mmHG which is the most common unit for blood pressure.

- The GP record specifies “overweight”; there is no fact on the actual weight and height of the individual. If possible, the individual responsible for the record - patient or clinical staff - should confirm the actual weight; if not possible this may remain unsolvable and therefore an element of information to be included with an uncertainty factor for further confirmation.
- In the GP report, the diagnosis and symptoms are written in plain English – and may be interpreted differently. All information should be translated into one formal code such as SNOMED for instance; based on the context, the code can be different. For instance, nausea as a finding has a different code than nausea/vomiting as a disorder; tiredness can be considered as “fatigue” or “chronic fatigue”. In this example, the system will pick “chronic fatigue” because of the presence of the adjective “regular” in front of the description; this however comes with an uncertainty factor.
- The lab result as well as the EHR file may be based on proprietary formats, rather than on standards such as HL7 with LOINC, SNOMED terminologies. Transformation of proprietary formats to a standard format can be done through mapping and transformation tools.
- Blood glucose is provided in different units between the lab file and the EHR one; even though these tests have been done at different times it would be easier for the treating staff to have the result in the same unit to check the evolution. This can be done through transformation tables.
- The name of the treating physician (Dr John Smith) is spelled differently. Is that the same person or not? This is a master data management problem that can be solved by checking master data records and deciding whether the match is sufficient to conclude that it is the same person. One name should be the “master”; all others are synonyms. In case there is no precise match, the PHD record responsible should be consulted.
- The date of the visit is different in all 3 data sources. Is the visit at the GP and in the lab on 9th June or 7th September 2018? Based on the context the lab result and the GP’s report have taken place on the same date. The PHD record responsible should be consulted on the time of the visit and blood test.

The AIDAVA project wants to solve these data quality issues in 2 steps as displayed in Figure 2.

1. Data Curation: harmonisation and integration of heterogeneous data sources into a semantic based representation, a Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG). This will be based on a detailed analysis of data quality issues and identification of automation potential, for further implementation in the project. The PHKG is an instance of a "Reference Health Ontology (RHO)" (see Figure 5) which includes the reference ontology description; each PHKG contains the data of the patient in the format specified in the RHKG following the curation process. This ensures interoperability across the PHKGs of the patients.
2. Data Publishing: transformation of the PHKG into a format required for data consumption/ secondary data use. From the PHKG, many transformations are possible supporting multiple use cases enabling the "**curate once, use many times**" principle of the AIDAVA project.

Figure 2. A two steps approach to data curation & publishing.

3.2 Overview of the problem we want to solve

The AIDAVA project aims at addressing two core problems.

1. Maximise automation in data curation & publishing⁵ of heterogeneous personal health data.
2. Empower individuals – patients or their deputy (e.g., family member, social worker) and data stewards/curators – in the curation and publishing of personal data, when automation is not possible due to lack of information.

These two aspects are further described in this section.

Figure 3. Problem we want to solve: core (in blue), enabling (in green)

To deploy the AIDAVA prototype developed during the project, and show its value, we need to add two "enabling" components

⁵ By "data curation & publishing" we mean the integration, harmonisation and quality enhancement (curation) and the transformation into a target format (publishing) of multimodal data, collected from various sources, to make it more usable by humans and machines.

- Gathering and "centralization" of personal data from heterogeneous data sources. These are use case specific and are addressed in the use case section.
- Identification of scientific questions demonstrating benefits for the clinicians and patients. These are the "secondary outcomes" of the assessment, specific for each use case, and further described in Chapter 4. Measurement of performance to the prototype - as a curation and publishing tool - are the primary outcomes specified in Chapter 5.

3.3 First Core problem to be solved: Data aggregation & curation

Current approaches for data curation and publishing are inadequate and costly.

- **Vertical curation** by expert data stewards: all records in one data source are curated together across all individuals. When the data are anonymized, records from a single individual cannot be linked across data sources; if data are pseudonymized they cannot be linked without the individual's consent which remains difficult to obtain. As a result, the curated datasets provide a partial view of citizens. In addition, as anonymized datasets can be used for different research purposes by different organisations, the same data can be curated multiple times, resulting in massive and wasteful duplication of effort. The objective of AIDAVA is to concentrate on the curation of the record of one patient (**Horizontal** curation), where the record includes all data on this single patient across different sources; the fact that all contextual information is available increases potential for automation in the curation process and encourages patient engagement in managing the quality of their data
- **Limited automation**, with risk of inconsistency and errors. Curation requires manual intervention by data stewards and trained clinical staff (medical student, nurse, PhD candidates...) when interpretation/extraction/semantic enrichment is needed. As staff change over time, there can be variation in this interpretation.
- **Existing data curation tools are siloed** and not always sufficient.
 - Current tools are siloed i.e., they solve a specific curation step (e.g., metadata management by Data Catalogue, transformation by ETL, concept extraction by Text Mining, entity reconciliation by Master Data Management, image feature extraction through Deep Learning, imputation of missing data through statistical methods), while all these steps might be needed across PHD of a single individual.
 - In some cases, existing curation tools are insufficient: e.g., limited number of concepts extracted with Text Mining versus innovative approaches based on NLP/DL).
- **Secondary data use of health data varies** and includes different requirements such as access to personal records by the patient, analytics for improved patient treatment (e.g., personalised medicine), analytics and AI in clinical research. The data - and formatting - needed to support these different requirements vary largely; as a consequence, there is limited reuse across "secondary data sets" developed to cover one data use, and each data consumer - or its deputy - most often needs to re-curate the primary data and build a different approach in the publishing (level of imputation, level of anonymization and aggregation, ...).

The AIDAVA project aims at addressing these problems by maximising automation in data curation & publishing of PHD so as to minimise manual intervention by individuals. Automation will be based on the definition of FAIRification process - focusing on the I (interoperability) and on the R (reuse) - detailing the different issues that limit interoperability and reuse of integrated health record and

describing the different steps and related tools needed to support data curation. Issues and tools will be linked to metadata that will support automation through orchestration of the use of curation tools based on the status of the data and the issue to be solved. This will be further detailed in WP2.

3.4 Second Core problem to be solved: Patient involvement

Currently there is no/limited empowerment of patients to control - let alone to increase the quality - of their personal data or that of their loved ones. Yet patients should be the first ones interested in having and accessing high quality health data to optimise quality of clinical care.

Citizen empowerment is a broad term covering multiple use cases and approaches[1]. In the context of the AIDAVA project, empowerment is considered in the context of management of personal health data. This is well described in Principle 3.3 of the MyData Declaration[2]. *'In a data-driven society, as in any society, individuals should not just be seen as customers or users of pre-defined services and applications. They should be considered free and autonomous agents, capable of setting and pursuing their own goals. They should have **agency and initiative**. We want individuals to be able to securely manage their personal data in their own preferred way. We intend to help individuals have the tools, skills and assistance to transform their personal data into useful information, knowledge and autonomous decision-making. We believe that these are the preconditions for fair and beneficial data-based relationships.*

This principle is rarely applied in health in Europe and not supported in the May 2022 version of the EHDS regulation where the data subjects have essentially a passive role: everything is done FOR them by providers and public health authorities, not much can be done BY them, except accessing their information. The first action to allow patients to be in command and manage their own data is to create the tools to make their clinical data easily accessible and improved - in a controlled way to secure data quality⁶ - by them.

Building on the MyData principle, the AIDAVA project is applying **active patient involvement** as a way to realise patient empowerment. To achieve this, several barriers must be tackled as described below. This list is the result of a combination of literature surveys, consolidated through brainstorming sessions within the consortium - including clinical staff and patient organisations. Patient organisations collected the input from patient consultants in the project and the results are added to the annex 10.1 and 10.2 of this document.

- INCENTIVES: To feel empowered and actively involved in managing my data, I need
 - *to be interested in my data.* While there is some evidence [3] that young and healthy people are not interested in their health data; there is also evidence [4] supporting great interest amongst patients and patient organisations to have access to and be more in control of their data, and get value out of the data. This lack of interest often comes along with lack of understanding of potential benefits;
 - *to understand the benefits.* Patients are often willing to contribute to managing and sharing their data but they need to see some benefits:

⁶ Data quality is addressed in Task 4.2; a data quality score will be defined including the skill level of the person who curated data

- **GOVERNANCE.** To feel empowered and actively involved in managing my data, I need some structure to ensure systematic and structural involvement of patients' co-creation through governance structures.

The AIDAVA project aims at addressing these barriers through different means as described in the table below.

Barrier	Approach to be developed in the AIDAVA project
INCENTIVES: need to be interested in my data and understand the benefits	Develop an explain ability module in the virtual assistant (Task 5.3) to increase awareness of value and benefits of high quality health data
DATA - difficult to access data and uncertainty on data security	To implement smooth access, we will <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● develop Data Transfer Agreements between hospitals, Health Data Intermediaries (HDI), and other linked entities ● build on emerging EU regulations such as the Data Governance Act⁸(DGA) and Data Act⁹ (DA) to maximise the role of HDI to support patients in managing their data and gather data such as GP record, medical devices, personal apps; ● assess potential to access data through national contact points as described in the emerging EHDS regulation[5]. This will be further developed through WP1, 2 and 4.
DATA - uncertainty on data quality	While AIDAVA will not change the raw data, it is expected that the curated data will be of higher quality by consolidating information across different data sources. Task 4.2 will develop a data quality score of the curated data, taking into account - among others - the skill level of the person who curated the data.
TOOLS - help me to access and manage consent	Build on Personal HDIs – compliant with the MyData operators reference model [6] - such as the 2 organisations we have in the consortium (P13-MIDATA and P14-DIGI.me)
TOOLS - support data correction, data update	Include relevant functionalities in the virtual assistant
TOOLS - help me understand my health	Out of scope of AIDAVA, though we will link AIDAVA with a 3rd party app allowing patients to visualise their data.
SKILLS	Develop different profiles (personas) that will interact with the AIDAVA prototype and clarify the most appropriate interaction model (Task 1.2)
GOVERNANCE	Develop a governance framework that supports data curation and publishing by patients, based on existing health data intermediaries;

⁸ The Data Governance Act (DGA) ([EUR-Lex - 52020PC0767 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)) was approved by the European Parliament in November 2021. It sets the regulatory framework for data intermediaries supporting citizens to mediate their data, i.e., access, integrate, manage storage and share their data in compliance with data privacy/GDPR. See

⁹ The Draft Data Act ([EUR-Lex - 52022PC0068 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)) was published in May 2022 and is still under negotiation at the time of writing this deliverable.

Barrier	Approach to be developed in the AIDAVA project
	identification of potential of new roles such as "patient community curator". This will be developed in Task 4.1 (D4.12)

Table 1. Barrier to patient involvement and proposed approach in AIDAVA

4. Description of Use Cases

The Use Cases below have been developed to support definition of the requirements and evaluation of the AIDAVA prototype in real life settings. This chapter describes the use case (current approach and proposed approach with AIDAVA); details on how AIDAVA will be assessed in these environments will be provided in *Deliverable D1.4. Assessment study (test, study initiation package)*, as part of Task 1.4.

Background on emerging regulations: Data Governance Act, Data Act, Health Data Intermediary.

One innovative aspect of AIDAVA is the involvement of HDI in supporting management of non-hospital data. The Data Governance Act – approved in November 2021 – provides a legal foundation for the establishment of these personal (Health) Data Intermediaries. MyData defined an operational framework supporting implementation of such data intermediaries, called MyData operators[6]. At the core of MyData operators are key functionalities such as identity management, consent management, data transfer and personal data store. In addition, MyData is running a MyData operators self-certification process. While Personal Health Data Intermediaries are not yet regularly in place, we can expect them to emerge in the coming 3 to 5 years. Two partners of AIDAVA - P13-MIDATA and P14-DME - are MyData operators and already manage mainly structured personal data, with patient consent.

The Data Act provides the legal foundation to ensure data holders – i.e., manufacturers of connected product & related services that collect data on EU citizens – transfer personal data to a data recipient indicated by the individual; this should be done through a “fair contract”, at cost, and data transferred should follow agreed digital standards. In the case of AIDAVA, we will use the HDIs of the project as data stewards for the patients.

4.1 Use Case 1. Toward an EU cross-border Breast Cancer registry

This use case focuses on hospitals and registries, to enhance the existing process of maintenance of breast cancer patient registries within hospitals, extended with data managed within Health Data Intermediaries (HDIs) to support maintenance of an EU wide registry.

Introduction to existing breast cancer registries

Austria	Within the MUG evaluation site: At MUG a local breast cancer database is maintained at the oncology institute via RedCap. To keep this database regularly up-to-date, students enter data manually e.g., in the course of their thesis work. However, this database is not part of the regular medical documentation, and will not be included in AIDAVA.
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	<p>National level: There is the national cancer registry, which is used to centrally record incidence, prevalence, and survival. Data on new cancer cases and deaths are recorded, but this registry does not map the disease processes. Other registries in Austria are more specialised in breast cancer, like the “BKFP - Brustkrebsfrüherkennungsprogramm”, or the “clinical tumor registry Austria for gynaecological tumors (KTR)”. In these registries also the disease processes are mapped, but they do not include all breast cancer cases across Austria.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National cancer registry (Statistik Austria): Every case of cancer and every death must be reported to the Central Statistical Office (Statistik Austria). The report is made via the hospitals. The medical director is responsible for the report and delegates this responsibility to various departments depending on the hospital (pathology, oncology). ● Clinical Tumor Registry Austria for Gynecological Tumors (KTR): 54 clinics from all over Austria participate in the Clinical Tumor Registry for Gynecological Tumors (KTR), but there is no complete coverage of Austria (e.g., MUG is not participating in KTR). The participating clinics/departments report new cases and follow-up cases of the cancer types included in the registry. Thereby clinical data on treatment and, if applicable, disease progression is recorded.
Estonia	<p>Within the NEMC evaluation site: The hospital's (NEMC) breast cancer register is created in the RedCap environment; it consists of 148 data fields and is entered manually. Data is mainly entered by 3 people from 3 different departments (secretaries, nurses). The data to be entered are mostly obtained from the hospital's information systems. The current registry started on 01.01.2022; previously it was only in excel.</p> <p>National level: There is also a national cancer registry in Estonia (<i>Estonian Cancer Register</i>), which is maintained by the Health Development Institute. The hospital registry and the national registry are not related, but the hospital is obliged to inform the keeper of the national register of all cancer cases.</p>
Netherlands	<p>Within the Maastricht Clinical evaluation site: MAASTRO clinic is part of the proton therapy centres consortium in the Netherlands. Therefore, the PROTRAIT registry is currently used as a national standard for the selection of patients for proton/photon therapy via the national indication protocol. The data are entered into an electronic data capture system (EDC) called “Libre Clinica” by the department of “Clinical Trials Office” (CTO) where the different “data managers” or “data importers” are assigned with the data entry from the electronic health record (EHR) systems of MAASTRO. The main challenge for them is to encounter the correct EHR field that a specific data item is registered to, for the manual data import, as there are a lot of “free-text” fields within the EHR system.</p>

	<p>National level: The scope of the existing breast cancer registries in the Netherlands (DICA, NKR, and PROTRAIT [7]) is to establish a standardised data collection pipeline for breast cancer and the improvement of decision making for treatment options. These datasets consist of tumour and treatment characteristics. DICA and NKR do not contain outcome data. PROTRAIT does contain outcome data, but generally only for breast cancer patients who are candidates to be treated with proton therapy.</p>
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Table 2. Overview of Breast Cancer registry across the 3 countries - and sites - involved in evaluation

Current approach and issues

Within hospital breast cancer registries, in scope of this use case, the data are stored most often within an excel spreadsheet or a proprietary local database, stored on a local server within the hospital. In the case of excel spreadsheet, access control is managed by procedure.

Data used for the registries is typically coming from different modules of the local EHR; it includes clinical narratives (free text) as well as structured data in variable formats, structures and standards. Curation for registry maintenance includes extraction of data from local EHR, identification of relevant concept/ code within clinical narratives, transformation of structured data in the appropriate standard and finally, manually entry into the registry. Maintenance of the registry is typically done manually by a responsible "registry steward", often supported by junior staff such as medical students in the context of their research project. Ideally a data quality process is in place to ensure that there are no mistakes in the overall process.

Figure 4. Maintenance of clinical registries today: a manual and tedious process done in silo

There are several issues with the existing approach:

1. Curation of data for a specific registry requires understanding of domain standards from the data stewards/curators; this mandates training and coaching of the medical staff (nurses, medical students, PhD, junior doctors...) acting as junior curators.
2. Tools supporting extraction of concept/code from the medical notes - written in sublanguage with abbreviations, acronyms, ambiguous terms - are rarely available. When/if they are, they have limited extraction capabilities, either forcing the curators to continue manual extraction of information or resulting in information not included in the registry.
3. Data from EHR records may not be complete for the specific purpose of the registries, and there is no easy access to other data sources such as GP records and patient apps. In today's practice no imputation of data is performed.

4. Curation of existing data to create registries is executed by different staff supporting the registry stewards. As manual curation of free text is not an accurate science, this may lead to variability in the final data set, due to differences in expertise of the curator.
5. As the same data (e.g., vitals, demographics) may be needed in different patient registries, the same data may be curated several times and be inconsistent across registries. As the number of clinical registries - needed to support different areas of research - increases, workload keeps increasing.
6. Each patient registry is typically stored in a specific, proprietary, format. Hence it is difficult to share outside the organisation where it is created, limiting the possibility of generating EU-wide repositories toward the emerging EHDS.

Proposed approach with AIDAVA

Overview

Location	<p>3 hospitals supported by respective Health Data Intermediary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Maastricht clinic in The Netherlands/Maastricht, supported by DME ● North Estonia Medical Center (NEMC) in Estonia/Tallinn, supported by MIDATA ● Graz University Medical Center (MUG) in Austria/Graz, supported by MIDATA
Description and Contribution to AIDAVA overall objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The use case will check how the AIDAVA prototype can support (and potentially replace some) existing staff who are maintaining patient registries currently. ● It will also check how patients could be more involved in the curation of their own data into such registries. ● Finally, it will verify the potential for federation across different hospitals and countries to build consistent, FAIR, EU-wide registries in the spirit of the European Health Data Space (EHDS), by executing the same query across the 3 registries – extracted from data curated by different staffs across the 3 different centres - and assess comparability and quality of the resulting data sets.
Stakeholders and interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breast cancer clinical registry staff: easier maintenance of the registry ● Patients: higher quality data and possibility to visualise own record ● Breast cancer specialist and breast cancer patient association: potential to expand scope of registry, and mainly access to cross-European interoperable data set ● HDI: demonstrate value as mediators of patient data, outside of hospital data.

Actors	<p>Data Curators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expert data curator (i.e., registry steward) ● Patient who corresponds to the inclusion/exclusion criteria defined in the protocol and who signed an informed consent <p>Data Consumers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breast Cancer specialist who can perform analytics on a "Breast Cancer" registry spread across the 3 sites ● Patient - through their HDI - who can visualise and query their medical record
Preconditions	<p>Scientific aspects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assessment Study Protocol approved by Ethical Committee ● Study Information Package (SIP) available to support signature of Informed Consent (IC) by patients <p>Data Privacy aspects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Informed Consent (IC) signed by patients ● Information Governance checklist review and Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) executed and approved in each organisation who requires it <p>Data Management/ handling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Transfer Agreement between the HDI and the non hospital data sources (GP data and personal app on breast cancer) ● Patients signed an agreement/informed consent with relevant HDI (MIDATA in Estonia) DME in the Netherlands is MedMij certified and no consent is needed. ● Data Transfer Agreement between the Hospital and the HDI ● AIDAVA prototype deployed

Table 3. Overview of Use Case 1 (Breast Cancer Registry)

User stories

User stories collected from participating sites and patient organisations illustrate the different stakeholders view and real life examples on how AIDAVA could help them in their current work/data curation process. They will be further expanded as part of the requirements in Task 1.3.

The sites wrote their user stories based on the viewpoint of clinicians, researchers and data curators/stewards and shared them with the work package members to better understand via examples what AIDAVA could solve.

Some examples include the expectation from clinicians and researchers to answer scientific questions using the data collected to breast cancer registries and data stewards' wishes to reduce the time spent interpreting, (re-)entering data to create or send data to a registry. Identifying possible human errors caused by manual work was also seen as a main benefit of AIDAVA.

Patient consultants highlighted in their stories the need to have a place to view their complete medical history and have the ability to share their data.

User story examples:

1. **As a doctor I want to** see the proportion of breast cancer patients undergoing breast conserving therapy with a radical resection of the tumour.

2. **As a researcher I want to** use highly structured/detailed information **so that** this is easily processed and does not require re-entering/interpretation.
3. **As a curator I want to** reduce work on tedious re-entering, searching and interpreting information (structured index and necessary data are in free text) **so that** the possibility of human errors is reduced.
3. **As a patient I want to** get access to my clinical data in a way I can understand and in a format I can use to obtain a second opinion.

High level process

The AIDAVA virtual assistant prototype will be deployed in a secure testing environment within the hospitals; it will work in different steps as displayed in the figure below.

Figure 5. Proof of concept "EU" Breast Cancer clinical registry across multiple sites while enabling patients to visualise their personal record (assumes pre-conditions in Table 3 are filled)

Step 1. Ingestion. The patient or data curator identifies data sources from the hospital EHR and from the patient health data intermediary, and requests transfer of personal data from these data sources into the AIDAVA TEMP DATA STORE available within the hospital testing environment. These data are stored in their original format. Extraction from the data sources can be done by the patient - if needed with the support of the local Data Curator or automated whenever possible; this will be further specified in the Data Transfer Agreements signed between the HDI managing the non-hospital data of the patient, and the hospital.

Step 2. Curation. The patient curator - or expert data curator - requests the AIDAVA virtual assistant to transform, integrate, potentially correct, and complete ingested data to generate a standardised representation of its individual's health record, the Personalised Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG). The

AIDAVA virtual assistant will maximise automation by orchestrating execution of relevant data curation tools for each curation step, and requesting input only when needed from the patient - at his/her level of health, digital and data literacy - or from the expert data curator when it is expected that the patient will not be able to answer.

Step 3. Publishing.

Case 3a. The expert data curator, responsible for the "EU" Breast Cancer registry in the local hospital, specifies with the help of the AIDAVA virtual assistant (1) the criteria to be met by patients to be included in the extract and (2) the list of data elements - and needed format - that should be extracted from the PHKG of the selected patients to generate the hospital local Breast Cancer extract.

Case 3c. In the same way, the HDI responsible for managing the data of a patient, specifies the data that should be extracted from the PHKG to a) support storage of the data in the HDI-side longitudinal health record of the patients and b) support visualisation and potential query through the selected 3rd party app. At the moment of writing the document, we intend to extract the data elements supporting the International Patient Summary (IPS) based on the HL7 FHIR profile. The 3rd party apps have not been identified yet; they could be different for the 3 sites.

In both cases, the specification of the extract can be done once and executed many times, whenever there is a refresh of the data sources and the PHKG. Once the extract's specification is confirmed, the AIDAVA virtual assistant extracts the data from the PHKG, performs the needed transformation to generate the target format required and stores the result in the relevant data store (case 3a) or transfers the data to the HDI (Case 3c).

The fact that we can generate 2 different extracts from the same PHKG, demonstrates a key principle of AIDAVA "**curate once, use many times**".

Step 4. Use.

Case 4a. The prototype virtual assistant deployed across different sites (NEMC, MUG and UM) will issue the same data extract in the specified format for an "EU" Breast Cancer registry across the 3 sites. To demonstrate interoperability of the resulting extracts, we will execute a set of "federated" queries (defined as secondary endpoints in the assessment of the prototype) across all 3 sites and consolidate the results into one single answer.

Case 4c. The 3rd party application, selected by the respective HDIs, will display, with consent of the patient, the patient data. The fact that the data used for patient record visualisation are coming from the same curated PHKG used for the registry will demonstrate interoperability and reuse of the underlying data.

Proposed Data sources

The following data sources are expected to be used to support this use case.

Source	Subcomponent	Short description on information use
EHR	Discharge Summary	A handover document that explains to other healthcare professionals why the patient was admitted, what has happened to them in hospital or clinic, and other information needed to continue care.
	Medical history	A record of information about a person's health. A personal

Source	Subcomponent	Short description on information use
		medical history may include information about allergies, illnesses, surgeries, immunizations, and results of physical exams and tests.
	Pathology reports	Contains morphological description, diagnosis, predictive and prognostic factors of tumour and pTNM. Includes reports of cytological specimens, biopsies and surgical specimens.
	Medical imaging reports	Contains the interpretations of images with the main goal of presenting the outcomes of the imaging procedure (mammogram, CT, MRI) of the patients to physicians.
	Progress notes	Progress notes are intended to provide an updated analysis of a patient's condition and progress during treatment.
	Surgical procedure descriptions	Detailed description of surgical procedure contains type(s) and extent of surgery, specimens removed and intraoperative pathology consultation report.
	Multidisciplinary meeting reports	Multidisciplinary meeting reports contain information about staging, treatment indications and decisions.
	TNM staging	TNM staging describes the stage of tumour.
	Prescribed medications	A prescription drug is a pharmaceutical that requires a medical prescription to be dispensed and their full list is provided usually at the end of a therapeutic encounter.
	Patient referral document	Patient referral documents contain information about current symptoms and disease, medical imaging. In some cases, it can be on paper.
Health Data intermediary	GP record	Contains notes and information from the GP on conditions, lab results, allergies, prescriptions. It is less detailed than any information contained in the EHR. As GP records typically cover the lifetime of a patient, they are offering a truly longitudinal perspective.
	Personal App	Specific breast cancer app - typically running on a smartphone - that assists the patient in understanding and potentially managing her conditions.

Table 4. Overview of data sources for Use Case 1 (Breast Cancer Registry)

4.2 Use Case 2. Secondary prevention of Atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease

While the breast cancer registry use case is primarily working on **population** registries across hospitals, this use case is focused on a **single patient** dossier. It is indeed focusing on enhancing the development and maintenance of a patient longitudinal health record for cardiovascular (CVD) patients.

Introduction to longitudinal health record for CVD patients

A longitudinal health record is valuable for healthcare providers (HCP) to ensure effective care. Health records include medical records collected within hospitals and other data that citizens collect during their lives (e.g., vaccinations, GP visits, interaction with health apps, self-assessments, wearable devices, etc.). This data is spread across multiple organisations in heterogeneous formats and using different - and most often, not linked - Patient-ID. Apart from the patient, and potentially a family GP, there is nobody responsible for this longitudinal record spanning the lifetime of a patient from cradle

to grave across all different medical problems. Without such a longitudinal record it is difficult to identify preventive measures and/or to define personalised treatment. Prevention is specifically important for patients who have experienced a myocardial infarction, as they are at risk of recurrent acute coronary events, progression of atherosclerosis and sudden cardiac arrest, in scope of this use case [9]. As AI systems are further developed that are able to characterise, aggregate and classify complex data, the concept of a prognostic digital twin of health has been suggested. This tool could augment human intelligence in disease diagnostic and prognostic decisions, risk assessment, intervention selection, outcome prediction and precision medicine[10]. The development of digital twins would require large sets of structured data, and AIDAVA could provide a tool that aids in the development of a digital twin.

Currents approach and issues

Today, availability of a high-quality longitudinal health record - relevant to cardiovascular diseases (CVD) and other diseases - remains a significant milestone to be achieved.

1. Health data are spread across multiple data sources and access to these data sources is difficult for individuals. While hospitals start to provide patient access apps, this represents only a fraction (estimated to be $\pm 40\%$) of health data. In some countries, National Health Data Hub (e.g. EHR or Digilugu in Estonia[12], MyHealth in Belgium[13], Health Data Hub in France[14], ELGA[15] in Austria etc) are emerging and allow individuals to access several types of personal data: e.g. hospital, vaccination, pharmacy, GP. However, these data are still incomplete and miss multiple data: legacy data in paper format as there is no efficient process for scanning them, clinical trial data collected by pharma companies who are reluctant to share these data for IP reasons, medical device data or personal health apps that are locked within the cloud of manufacturers.
2. In addition, these health data are not always interoperable: they are stored with potentially different identifiers, different master data (i.e., name of organisation or name of physician), in many different formats, often with redundancies and inconsistencies; it is difficult to make sense of this information for the patient and for carers.
3. These personal health data also include a lot of text-based reports - same as for breast cancer narratives - and are most often phrased (scientific terms and abbreviations) in such a way that patients cannot understand.
4. **There is no single person or organisation responsible for an integrated health record**, except the patient itself (who has no tool to manage this record). With the emergence of Personal Health Data Intermediaries and with the development of Data Act, Findability and Accessibility in the FAIR sense should be facilitated for patients. As an example, a PGO - Patient Gegevens Organisatie/ Patient Data Organisation - in the Netherlands can be selected by a patient to manage his/her personal data; data transfer with PGOs is enabled by a national data transfer framework called MedMij[16]. However, curation of personal health data to provide an integrated, high quality reusable longitudinal record still requires expert data stewards which may not be affordable.

Proposed approach

Overview

Location	<p>3 hospitals supported by respective Health Data Intermediary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Maastricht University Medical Center (MUM) in The Netherlands/Maastricht , supported by DME ● North Estonia Medical Center (NEMC) in Estonia/Tallinn, supported by MIDATA ● Graz University Medical Center (MUG) in Austria/Graz, supported by MIDATA
Description and Contribution to AIDAVA overall objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It will check how AIDAVA can involve citizens - or their deputy - to become their own master i.e., to manage their own longitudinal health record as they are indeed the main actors who are interested and legally able to manage their complete record. ● It will also check how “community data curators¹⁰” could help patients and effectively replace them, with their consent. Community curators are non-patients, with a readiness to help patients to maintain and curate their data. Community curators would also have an advanced training to enable them to become skilled data curators. The concept of community curator is new; it could be a new type of job. ● It will check how it can benefit HCPs by deriving risk metrics on patients, extracted from the patient record. ● Finally, the use case will verify the potential for reuse of the generated longitudinal record by demonstrating that different patient applications (be it for patient visualisation or for derivation of the same risk metrics) can be smoothly integrated across different HDIs in different countries, by extracting the needed data in the required format for the selected application.
Stakeholders and interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CVD Patients: higher quality data and possibility to visualise own record ● Cardiovascular specialist and heart patient association: potential to have smoother access to important metrics/ risk score that must be managed ● Health Data Intermediary: demonstrate value as mediators of patient data, outside of hospital data.
Actors	<p>Data Curators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patient who corresponds to the inclusion/exclusion criteria defined in the protocol and who signed an informed consent ● Community curator who has been trained as experienced data curators <p>Data Consumers:</p>

¹⁰ The concept of a community data curator is new and introduced by AIDAVA. The idea is to identify people who are ready to support patients in their community in curating data and to train them to become equivalent to expert data curators; community curators could also be people that help patients to execute data curation themselves. As the project evolves, we will further describe this role. For the first generation of the prototype, we expect that the community curator will be the research nurse supporting the evaluation. For G2, it could be patients coming for instance from patient associations.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cardiovascular specialist who has access to an automatically computed risk score (instead of having to compute it manually) and can more effectively monitor CVD risks. • Patient - through his/ her HDI - who can visualise and query their medical record
Preconditions	<p>Scientific, Data Management/ handling aspects: same as for Breast Cancer UC</p> <p>Organisational aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community curator role defined and candidates identified (through patient association or hospital)

Table 5. Overview of Use Case 2 (prevention of ACVD)

User stories

In the case of CV, the main benefits were seen on different levels:

A primary outcome for AIDAVA is to be patient-centred and would be tied to the patients' (or their carers') ease of access to their complete data set and their ability to improve the quality (e.g., by inserting missing or correcting wrong dates) of their data. The ability to add data from wearables or medical applications would also improve the completeness of their health data.

For clinicians and researchers as secondary users of data, in this use case AIDAVA will give a better overview of the patient by including third party devices integrated with the patient's medical data and provide notifications of incorrect values or inconsistencies in the data. A SMART risk score provided by AIDAVA based on the data will alert the clinicians and prompt them to work together with the patient to reduce the chance of a recurrent cardiovascular event.

1. **As a doctor/nurse I want to** use health data which is intelligently retrieved from different systems and put into a new form, **so that** incorrect data is identified and corrected.
2. **As a patient I want to** have access to my longitudinal personal health data in a secure and digital format, **so that** I can access it and used at any time.

Patient consultants provided some concrete examples,

- a. *Today I staple all my medical letters. When I need them, I have to look and search. One time I needed medical information on holiday. I didn't digitise my medical letters, so I had to send the hospital an email to send me my medical letters via pdf. Very time consuming. If you are ill, you will not have the time or constitution to manage all your belongings.*
- b. *The first thing I do is I scan it [medical results, letters, etc.] with the scanner of my mobile and store it in my phone. A patient like me when you open my phone you see a forest of files with my medical information. So basically, I have a storage room with hundreds of documents with my personal health data, but nothing can be done with it because it is not easy to find when I need specific information and it is not curated.*
- c. *To draw comparisons to former data (longitudinal data). [...] When I get my blood checked, I receive an overview of my blood values compared to former blood checks*

and compared to normal values. That's perfect and I also wish that for all medical examinations.

High level process

We will work with the Virtual Assistant in 4 steps

Figure 6. Assessment of SMART risk score - in the same way across 3 sites - while enabling patients to visualise their personal record (assumes pre-conditions mentioned in Table 5 are met)

Step 1. Ingestion. Similar to Breast Cancer use case with the addition of medical device data.

Step 2. Curation. Similar to Breast Cancer with the addition of medical device data, and with a "community curator" identified within the hospital as "expert curator".

Step 3. Publishing.

Case 3b. The AIDAVA Virtual assistant supports extraction and transformation of the patient PHKG into the format needed for computation of the SMART risk score. The 3 sites (NEMC, MUG and UM) where the prototype is deployed will provide extracts in the same required forma.

Case 3c. Similar to Breast Cancer use case.

Step 4. Use.

Case 4b. To demonstrate interoperability of the PHKG and of the resulting extracts, we will integrate the same software, the SMART risk algorithm that computes the risk, in the 3 sites and provide results to the cardiovascular specialists.

Case 4c. Similar to Breast Cancer use case.

Proposed Data Sources

The following data sources are expected to be used to support this use case

Source	Subcomponent	Short description on information use
EHR	Discharge Summary	A handover document that explains to other healthcare professionals why the patient was admitted, what has happened to them in hospital, and other information needed to continue care
	Progress Notes	Progress notes are intended to provide an updated analysis of a patient's condition and progress during treatment.
	Laboratory reports	Describe the results of laboratory tests performed for the patient samples
	Medical imaging reports	Contains the interpretations of images with the main goal of presenting the outcomes of the imaging procedure (e.g., X-ray, MRI) of the patients to physicians
	Medical history	A record of information about a person's health. A personal medical history may include information about allergies, illnesses, surgeries, immunizations, and results of physical exams and tests.
	Echocardiography report	Echocardiography is a diagnostic tool for diagnosis and follow-up of heart disease and its report provides the interpretation of the medical imaging procedure
	Coronary angiography report	Coronary angiogram is a procedure that uses X-ray imaging of the heart's blood vessels and its report provides the interpretation of the medical imaging procedure
	Prescribed medications	A prescription drug is a pharmaceutical that requires a medical prescription to be dispensed and their full list is provided usually at the end of a therapeutic encounter.
	Ambulance record	A record of care provided during the ambulance stage of treatment.
	Emergency department record	A record of care provided during the emergency department stage of treatment.
Health Data intermediary	ICU/CICU progress notes	Provide an updated analysis of a patient's condition and progress during the ICU stay.
	GP system	Contains notes and information from the GP on conditions, lab results, allergies, prescriptions. It is less detailed than any information contained in the EHR. As GP records typically cover the lifetime of a patient, they are offering a truly longitudinal perspective.
	Personal App	General health data app - typically running on a smartphone - that assists the patient in understanding and potentially managing her conditions. (Google Fit app; Apple Health app)
	Connected medical device	Certified digital devices that help gather vitals (and potentially many other parameters) directly from the patient. One approved medical device will be identified for this use case.

Table 6. Overview of data sources for Use Case 2 prevention of ACVDy)

5 Evaluation criteria to measure performance of prototype

As mentioned above, the AIDAVA prototype will be assessed at the level

- **Primary outcomes** are related to the appropriateness for use of the tool to maximise automated data curation and publishing as well as engagement with patients - as data curator - rather than expert data curator, whenever automation is not possible. It is aimed at the users of the prototype.
- **Secondary outcomes** are related to the use of data published by the prototype; it is aimed at the consumers of AIDAVA (or data users) i.e., scientists and patients visualising the health record.

Secondary outcomes are use case specific; they have been introduced with the use case descriptions and will be finalised with the clinical aspect as part of the Assessment protocol in D1.4. Primary outcomes have been discussed during a brainstorming at the December 2022 workshop in Tallinn, building on the metrics identified in the proposal. They are further described here; they will be included as well in the Assessment protocol.

5.1. Metrics defined in the proposal

The table provides the list of metrics identified at the proposal stage

Parameter & metric	Description	Scale/Outcome (estimates)
#1. Efficiency: Decrease workload in quality enhancement of data <i>% time spent in data curation versus analytics</i>	Data curation & publishing for clinical registries is typically performed by data stewards supported by students or staff with data engineering and medical backgrounds. It is generally accepted that data stewards spend ~60% of their time curating data[18], and 20% in analytics. With AIDAVA, we expect to decrease workload in data curation	Decrease time spent on curation from ~60% to <30%, ideally < 20%.
#2. Efficiency: Maximise reuse of data by increasing their quality <i>score (consistency, completeness, conformity, semantic accuracy)</i>	Reuse of health data is crucial for enhancing health care and accelerate clinical research. Poor health data quality not only jeopardises its reuse but also generates patient frustration, employee distrust, decreased efficiency and results in poor and ineffective decisions. We expect that AIDAVA will increase the quality of collected data, maximising their value and reusability. Scores will be defined as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● agree with site representatives (patients and Health Care Providers) on sample “high value” core data items for clinical decision making, patient safety, and patient self-management 	Increase quality score by a factor 4 to 5; decrease time to answer clinical questions by up to 20%.

Parameter & metric	Description	Scale/Outcome (estimates)
	<p>tools. (Note: these ones are usually not captured in a structured and coded form but available in free text notes or inferred across other data points)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assess from sample anonymised data sets the baseline level of data quality using four dimensions based on published methods ● monitor these dimensions as we develop and deploy AIDAVA solutions, and aim to have the declared increases across the four dimensions. 	
<p>#3. Activity/ acceptance: Maximise involvement of citizens in curating health data <i>% citizens ready and able to curate data with a VA (and become citizen-curators)</i></p>	<p>AIDAVA enables three possibilities: the citizen/patient</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) wants to be involved in data curation 2) does not want to be involved, but wants to assign a deputy 3) does not want to assign anyone, but consents to the curation of its data. <p>Currently, none are viable options, as few citizens control their data, and data curation is the realm of experts. We believe in the long-term achievability of Option 1. For that, citizen participation must be facilitated with human-AI collaboration, opening the doors for people across age, gender, and education to interact with health data in ways that are not more difficult than interacting with other personal data on social media.</p>	<p>Increase from ~0% active data curation, today to ~5 %, growing to 20% in the next 10 years.</p> <p>(Own estimate; note: one citizen "curator" would curate data of several relatives).</p>
<p>#4. Added value: Maximise reuse of content of clinical narratives, while retaining their use in clinical practice <i>ratio of structured data extracted from text with VA versus existing practice</i></p>	<p>Anywhere from 40-80% of health data is in narrative form and hospital staff face increased pressure to maximise structured data entry to facilitate reuse. While this can be beneficial in fields with structured content linked to procedures (e.g., ophthalmology), not everything in medicine can be predefined. Forcing structured data entry may lead to low data quality, which may also affect clinical care quality. AIDAVA aims to allow clinicians to keep working with narrative notes by maximising the amount of structured data that can be extracted from them.</p>	<p>Increase reuse from estimated ~1% today to ~50% (in languages used in the project)</p>

Table 7. Original metric proposed to measure the performance of the AIDAVA prototype

5.2. Update of metrics after brainstorming session

Parameter	Original metric	Proposed metric (and rationale for change)
<p>#1. Efficiency: Decrease workload in quality enhancement of data</p>	<p>% time spent in data curation versus analytics</p>	<p>Compare average time spent in curating needed data elements in</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G0 (current situation) • G1 (generation 1 of the prototype) • G2 (generation 1 of the prototype). <p>Check the amount of data curated in the average time: are there more data being curated together with the ones needed to support the use case</p> <p>The focus on AIDAVA is on data quality enhancement. It seems more relevant to compare the impact of the 2 generations (G1 and G2) of the tool versus the current situation (G0) on that aspect.</p>
<p>#2. Efficiency: Maximise reuse of data by increasing their quality, availability and interoperability</p>	<p>score (consistency, completeness, conformity, semantic accuracy)</p>	<p>Score measuring related to volume, completeness consistency, availability of metadata & semantic accuracy, conformity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • volume (number of data items curated) • completeness (number of missing items) • consistency (number of consistency checks that fail) • availability of context information (metadata) • conformity (compliance with reference health ontology) <p>The proposed parameters represent the one deemed as important for the majority of stakeholders from their points of views (patients, HCPS, data scientist, computer scientist, HDI, ...). The actual score will be defined in Task 4.2.</p>
<p>#3. Activity/ acceptance: Maximise involvement of citizens in curating health data</p>	<p>% citizens <u>ready</u> and <u>able</u> to curate data with a VA (and become citizen-curators)</p>	<p>Request to fill a structured questionnaire (adapted from a System Usability Scale - see Annex - with additional questions such as</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I would you recommend AIDAVA to your friend, colleague, or family member • I am interested / ready to work with AIDAVA I when available on the market • I understand the purpose of data curation

Parameter	Original metric	Proposed metric (and rationale for change)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>I am ready to spend the needed time to ensure proper data curation</i> • <i>The curation process was too long for me</i> <p>The best way to measure acceptance of the AIDAVA prototype is to raise a set of questions through a structured questionnaire; we checked different possibilities including Telehealth Utility questionnaire [19] and System Usability Scale [20]. We need however to ensure that the final questionnaire is not too long (10 questions is a good target)</p>
#4. Added value: Maximise reuse of content of clinical narratives, while retaining their use in clinical practice	<i>ratio of structured data extracted from text with VA versus existing practice</i>	Increase reuse from estimated ~1% today to ~50% (within the two use cases and three languages used in the project). E.g., How many data fields in the sample breast cancer registry (created in the project to test the prototype) can the VA find in narratives automatically compared to existing practice?

Table 7. Final metric proposed to measure the performance of the AIDAVA prototype

All metrics will be further described as part of Task 1.4 in the Assessment Protocol (Deliverable 1.4).

6 Resources needed for deployment & testing

To understand the readiness to deploy the AIDAVA prototype and to make sure to properly plan this deployment by addressing the different organisational, ethical, and technical constraints - we asked each of the sites to fill a structured questionnaire. These questionnaires will be further used to plan deployment for G1 and G2

In this section, we first provide a high-level description of the content questionnaire and then provide an overview of the answers from all sites that were discussed across partners at the Tallinn workshop in December 2022.

6.1. Description of the site questionnaire

The following aspects were included.

1. Status of use case across sites. High-level summary of the status of the two use cases.
2. Description of roles involved and mapping with local roles. Roles included

- Enablers such as ICT staff, Ethical Committee
 - User of the systems i.e., patient curator, expert data curator or community curator
 - Data consumers (or data users) i.e., breast cancer specialists, cardiovascular specialists and the patients themselves (when they visualise their data)
3. Organisational aspects and committees. Description of the different committees - such as the Ethical Committee - that need to approve deployment and evaluation of the prototype. This includes a high-level description of the process to be followed and the time needed for approval.
 4. Description of data sources available locally and to be used by the prototype (with the consent of the patient).
 5. Data Portability and Data Transfer Agreement mechanism in place within the hospital.
 6. Technical aspects and concerns when deploying a medical device prototype such as AIDAVA within a running environment of the site.

6.2. Overview of the answers across sites

The section below summarises the answers across all organisations

- All organisations have answered the questions presented in the site's questionnaire. They presented the status of their activities as well as the technical aspects.
- All hospitals have in-depth experience in the identified Therapeutic areas with specialist clinical teams. In the case of Breast cancer, they participate in the local and/ or national breast cancer registry.
- All hospitals have Ethical Committees that must provide approval - based on a well-documented research protocol - on evaluation of AIDAVA within their environment. The time to get Ethical Approval - including back & forth questions - is estimated to be around 3 months. HDIs also have ethical checks - though lighter than hospitals - through Ethical Boards that need to confirm adherence to their principles and contracts.
- All hospitals support data portability - typically by sending PDF files generated from the medical record of the patient. These PDF files can be sent to secure email or - in the case of record that include the images - with a USB stick.
- All partners are familiar with Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) to be used in AIDAVA
 - Between data holders (patient app, devices) and HDI: this is core to the HDI business model.
 - Between HDI and Hospital (transferring data to the hospital for integration and curation, and transferring agreed extract from the PHKG to the HDI for patient visualisation). In the Netherlands, there is no need to have such a formal agreement for data intermediaries (like DME) who are MedMij certified; for Estonia and Graz, a formal DTA will be required
- From a technical integration aspect all hospital partners who need to install the docker instance where AIDAVA will reside will be able to accommodate for this.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable clarifies the problem we want to solve and documents in detail the 2 use cases that will support deployment and testing of the AIDAVA prototype. It contributes to building a **common vision of the objectives of the project** across the different partners - clinicians and computer scientists

- which is critical to deliver a successful project as a consortium. It also contributes to **understanding the approach to deployment and testing**, and provides the needed information for effective planning of this deployment.

8 Next steps

This deliverable - and the associated material gathered during Task 1.1. - is the basis of several deliverables of the projects and more specifically

- support to the identification of personas (D1.8),
- scoping for the business requirements (D1.3),
- detailed definition of the assessment study (D1.4),
- support for smooth deployment of Generation 1 (G1) of the AIDAVA prototype (D1.6).

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10 Annexes

10.1 Patient empowerment - EHN (Cardio)

To feel empowered and actively involved in managing my data with AIDAVA, I need...	Strongly agree				Agree				Disagree			
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P1	P2	P3	P4	P1	P2	P3	P4
INCENTIVES:												
to be in control of my data and understand its value	X	X	X	X								
to understand and improve own health condition	X	X	X	X								
to share data with any care providers who require it	X	X	X	X								
to share data for the common good (research)	X		X	X		X						
SOLUTION FOR DATA RELATED ISSUES:												
easy access to my data data.	X	X	X	X								
understand how good/complete /correct are my data	X		X	X		X						
feel certain my data are secure i.e. access is under my control	X			X		X						
feel certain my data are secure i.e. access is regulated by law (governments)				X	X	X						
TOOLS:												
help me to access and manage my data with no/ limited technical knowledge						X		X				
to support data quality enhancement in my data					X	X		X				
to manage consent for sharing my data	X					X		X				
to help me to understand my health condition	X	X	X	X								
adapted to my personal background and context.	X	X	X	X								
SKILLS:												
a minimum set of skills (digital, data, health literacy)	X	X	X	X								
GOVERNANCE:												
structure to ensure systematic / supported involvement	X	X	X	X								
OTHERS ?												
...												

10.2 Patient empowerment - ECPC (Breast cancer)

To feel empowered and actively involved in managing my data with AIDAVA, I need...	Strongly agree				Agree				Disagree				Strongly Disagree				Do not know			
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P1	P2	P3	P4	P1	P2	P3	P4	P1	P2	P3	P4	P1	P2	P3	P4
INCENTIVES:																				
to be in control of my data and understand its value	X	X	X	X																
to understand and improve own health condition				X	X		X		X											
to share data with any care providers who require it	X	X		X			X													
to share data for the common good (research)		X			X		X	X												
SOLUTION FOR DATA RELATED ISSUES:																				
easy access to my data data.	X	X	X	X																
understand how good/complete /correct are my data			X	X	X	X														
feel certain my data are secure i.e. access is under my control	X	X			X				X											
feel certain my data are secure i.e. access is regulated by law (governments)		X	X	X	X															
TOOLS:																				
help me to access and manage my data with no/ limited technical knowledge			X	X		X			X											
to support data quality enhancement in my data			X	X		X											X			
to manage consent for sharing my data			X		X	X			X											
to help me to understand my health condition			X	X					X	X										
adapted to my personal background and context.			X		X	X			X											
SKILLS:																				
a minimum set of skills (digital, data, health literacy)		X	X	X	X															
GOVERNANCE:																				
structure to ensure systematic / supported involvement					X	X	X	X												
OTHERS ?																				
block, change or manage personal data			X	X																

10.3 System usability Scale (Standard version)

The example below is from [20])

	System usability Scale (Standard version)	Strongly Disagree				Strongly Agree
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0	0	0	0	0
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex	0	0	0	0	0
3	I thought the system was easy to use	0	0	0	0	0
4	I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	0	0	0	0	0
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0	0	0	0	0
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	0	0	0	0	0
7	I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0	0	0	0	0
8	I found the system very awkward to use	0	0	0	0	0
9	I felt very confident using the system	0	0	0	0	0
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	0	0	0	0	0